
Deliverable D-JIP2-3.2

Thematic workshops

Workpackage: 3

Responsible Partner: SVA

Contributing partners:

APHA, BfR, FHI, FOHM, INIAV, RIVM,
APHA, ISS, NVI, Sciensano, SLV, WBVR

GENERAL INFORMATION

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TITLE

Title D- Thematic workshops on detection of short-term and long-term signals, April 10-12, Uppsala, Sweden

Thematic workshops within the tasks 3.1 on “Explore current ways for exchanging signals between countries and cross disciplines – pathway analysis” and 3.2 “Select tools for Horizon scanning and signal detection” were organised during the Annual Meeting of the One Health European Joint Programme funded COHESIVE project and hosted by SVA (National Veterinary Institute, Uppsala, Sweden).

1. Aim

The COHESIVE EJP Joint Integrative Project has four major objectives:

- 1) *Stimulating One Health approaches at the national level within EU countries*
- 2) *Roadmap towards an EU zoonoses risk-assessment of risk-analysis structure.*
- 3) *Design and test a common platform for the collection and analysis of surveillance and outbreak data on (foodborne) zoonoses.*
- 4) *Capacity building within and between EU countries at several levels within the area of zoonotic diseases.*

The workshops focused on short-term och long-term signals: workshop 1 on the exchange of signals of potential zoonotic events and workshop 2 on an inventory and analysis of tools for long-term signals within one health using horizon scanning.

2. Workshop 1: current ways of exchanging signals within countries, between countries and across disciplines

The aim of the task 3.1 is to identify factors that contribute to a well-functioning system for sharing signals on zoonotic events, barriers for sharing signals and suggestions for improvement. Prior to the workshop Maria Nöremark, the task leader of 3.1 had contacted the participants of the COHESIVE project by email presenting a proposal for conducting the task. The plan was to explore current ways of exchanging signals on zoonotic events by applying qualitative methods, thus performing semi-structured interviews in with persons working within public health, animal health and food safety.

Programme:

Wednesday April 10, 2019

- 14.15-15.00 Introduction, presentations of the participants, definition of the task
- 15.30-16.15 Discussion on the goals and aims of the task
- 16.15-17.00 Discussion on practical questions on performing the task, questionnaire guideline

Thursday April 11, 2019

- 13.30-14.15 Discussion on the interviews to be conducted: type of organisations, authorities and persons to be targeted: public health, animal health, food safety, central and regional authorities

14.15-15.00 Discussion on methods for transcriptions and data analysis

Friday April 12, 2019

09.00-09.45 Discussion on how to deal with anonymity (person, organisation, country level). Discussion on a data management plan

09.45-10.30 Discussion on appropriate time schedule and deadlines for deliverables within the project, report and manuscript. Discussion on tasks to perform.

The workshop was a continuation of the information gathered at the COHESIVE inspiratory workshop in November, 2018 at APHA and through the questionnaire circulated among EJP partners. The structures within One Health in the European countries vary. Also, the systems for exchanging of signals may differ greatly within and between countries, between disciplines and between regulated and less-regulated pathogens. In order to explore the experiences on sharing of signals and the barriers, weaknesses and strengths of various systems a qualitative approach with deep interviews was considered the most suitable way to address the issue. A traditional questionnaire may not be able to catch these items.

It was concluded at the workshop that the aim of this study is to explore experiences among persons working at different positions in the field of zoonoses of sharing signals (definition below) within and between countries. The study focuses on signals of zoonotic or suspect zoonotic agents but is not limited to certain species, routes of transmission or if the pathogen/disease is regulated or not. The results will hopefully be used when revising existing systems, or when developing new systems for signal-sharing. In long term – improved systems for signal sharing can contribute to earlier detection and control of ongoing events and thus minimizing the consequences of such events. The information will be forwarded to participating countries, EFSA, ECDC and the European Commission and hopefully published in an article.

A signal was defined as a kind of indication of a potential outbreak, cluster, emergency, unexpected rise in prevalence or a new infection. The signal can be identified via an alarm in an existing system, via a “gut feeling” that something is going on which can be based on an information from laboratory reports or via media coverage, or through personal contact. For the purpose of this task it was decided not to focus on signals resulting in large outbreaks or unexpected events but also to potential false alarms or limited events.

The main purpose of this study is not to identify or describe in detail all different routes that signals can be detected or shared (i.e. not to give full detailed description of all existing systems). However, including some examples of systems can be useful to increase understanding.

When discussing the interviews it was decided to perform five interviews per country but participants could interview more persons if they were interested or considered it necessary. The purpose of the task is not to provide with a full detailed description of all existing systems in all countries and disciplines, but to describe examples and experiences of various systems. Moreover, the purpose is not to define exactly what constitutes a signal, but the study focus on the point in time when a signal has already been perceived as a signal, and how the information was communicated and shared.

It was decided to interview persons at both regional and national levels in order to provide with a fuller picture of the reality. The participants were to select the interviewees. Preferably, two persons should perform the interviews, and analyse the data. The selection of the interview objects should be performed using purposeful sampling. Correspondingly, it would be good to interview persons in areas where you know that capturing and forwarding signals is challenging.

Furthermore, the participants agreed on not performing a study on comparisons between countries or systems. The persons interviewed within the task will represent a sample of persons working at different levels, in different countries and systems, investigating whether there are common experiences on factors contributing to well-functioning systems and common experiences on barriers or hinders for sharing signals.

Discussions on the questionnaire guideline resulted in a draft guideline which was finalised and sent to the participants after the meeting. The participants agreed on starting with the selection of the interviewees during spring of 2019 and continuing with the interviews, transcriptions and a preliminary data analysis. The participants agreed upon meeting in autumn 2019 to discuss the preliminary findings and later compiling a scientific report.

3. Workshop on selection of tools for Horizon scanning and signal detection

The aim of this task is to perform an inventory and analysis of tools for horizon scanning regarding one health issues.

Programme

Wednesday April 10, 2019

13:00-14:15 Introduction of participants and overview of the task – Joint follow up of the COHESIVE Questionnaire - identification of needs

Thursday April 11, 2019

13:30-15:00 Inventory of Horizon scanning teams and how to proceed of tools for Horizon Scanning

The task 3.2 workshop participants discussed their experiences with horizon scanning. Robin Simons described that APHA has done quite some work related to horizon scanning. Ludovico Sepe also mentioned that BfR are involved in various risk assessment and foresight activities. Anders Wallensten said that Public Health Agency of Sweden have done some of this, but it is time consuming to do it. Karin Nyberg gave an horizon scanning example on how the National Food Agency in Sweden work and that they were able to predict that insects as a food would be an issue. Elina Lahti and Rickard Knutsson mentioned activities at SVA and also some of the coordination activities related to funding from the Swedish Civil Contingencies Agency. Gry Grøneng (NIPH) said that they are interested to get more information. Discussion took place about quantitative and qualitative methods. A FAO horizon scanning paper was shown. This paper has a focus on food safety and not one health, but it is a useful set up. Based on this paper the time frame, i.e if it should be 6 month or a bit longer i.e. 2 to 3 years ahead was discussed. There are many one health initiative and duplication of work shall be avoided and added value must be addressed. After discussion using horizon scanning for 2-3 years foresight might be something to go forward with.

Follow up on the COHESIVE Questionnaire

In 2018 a COHESIVE questionnaire was distributed to partners. The questionnaire contained some questions related to horizon scanning and the outcome of the questionnaire was discussed. The workshop focused the discussion on to see if any of the challenges identified could be addressed. A general interest was to investigate if horizon scanning could be integrated into any existing One Health bodies or organisations. Various stakeholders concerning coordination of Horizon scanning could be considered. It was suggested that the upcoming Task 3.2 session on the 11th of April 2019 should focus on these issues.

Added value of Horizon scanning

On the second day of the workshop some more reflections and insights were discussed. Duplication of work is not appropriate and since there are many various one health initiatives it is essential that task 3.2 have this perspective. Risk assessment of zoonotic diseases is well established and to continue with this task work the added value of conducting mid-long term assessment and horizon scanning must be reviewed. There are many mid-long term phenomena that can cause spread of zoonotic diseases and it is of interest to understand these phenomena, how they evolve over time, how they can be prevented, and how to consider and assess these risk phenomena. Consequently, it might be a need to address why to consider doing horizons scanning in a one health approach. Task 3.2 workshop participants had different views but in general it was identified that a horizon one health scanning of 2-5 years ahead should be a focus of the task work.

Stakeholders

Since horizon scanning is complicated and require quite some staff resources the work time allocated must be addressed from the beginning. Competent stakeholders must be identified on an early basis and a workshop discuss took place on identifying some tentative stakeholders. Followings stakeholders were addressed:

- ECDC
- EFSA
- OIE
- WHO
- FAO
- EU COM
- National Gov offices.

To get in more engaged about the stakeholders workshop exercise was conducted. Each participants were given a paper to be filled in. Two groups discussed various stakeholders views and following were identified from the two groups:

“Stakeholder view/feelings” about One Health Horizon scanning	Group 1	Group 2
Think & Feel	Think that it is positive and valuable to do and feel responsibility	Think it is important and strategic but feel that it is difficult
Hear	Many is talking about it, hear information from various sources and look into databases	Done elsewhere at other agencies, need to foresee things, formal responsibility and expectations to conduct One Health HS.
See	Media reporting, a lot of informal meeting with experts, information from other stakeholders.	Disasters and outbreaks can be avoided, HS reports can be questioned, unofficial reports.
Say & Do	Communicate findings to the public, avoid information failure mandate to act, initiate surveillance.	Communicate findings to the public, have a good system in place but some info may be restricted.
Pain	Collaboration with other sectors is complicated, requires resources, difficult to get sustainability and correct data/competences, uncertainty	Resource intensive, creating wrong conclusions leads to lower credibility, uncertainty.

Gain	Proactiveness, preparedness, disasters/outbreaks, credibility	better prevent better	Better preparedness, prevent disasters/outbreaks, better credibility
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Horizon scanning teams

Getting the right experts is difficult and it must be in a balanced manner. Mid-to long term foresights requires participants from all sectors/domains:

- Environment
- Food
- Human
- Animal

In the 3.2 task group there are competences/partners covering food, human and veterinary medicine. Integration of environment/climate competences is currently an issue for the coming task work. Partners were asked to contribute with recommendations regarding expertise from the environment/climate domain. An important outcome of this workshop was the formation of the 3.2 task team. So far partners from Sweden, UK, Germany, Belgium and Norway have indicated an interest to be engaged in the team.

Short briefing of the 3.2 task workshops and plenum discussion

The outcome of the task 3.2 sessions was shortly presented. The rationale and added value for mid to long term foresight was described. The importance of tentative end users and stakeholders were covered in a stakeholder workshop exercise. During the plenary meeting it was suggested that it might be of interest to make use of the horizon scanning methodology at the upcoming COHESIVE meeting most likely in November 2019. A pilot and joint one health horizon scanning activity could be arranged at this COHESIVE meeting if there is an interest. It is a good option to get critical